

Optimal Design of a New Configuration of the Distributed Generation Units using Grey Wolf and Dragonfly Optimizers

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Abstract – Distributed generation units are used to share the loads with the conventional power plants or may be used to supply the power to the loads individually. Wind turbine (WT), photovoltaic (PV), storage battery (SB), fuel cell (FC), gas turbine (GT), and micro-turbine (MT) are considered the most distinctive distributed generation units, which are used in this type of applications. There are much combinations or configurations of these power sources, where the WT may be combined only with the PV. This combination might be combined with the SB. Or WT, PV, and SB are connected with the FC to form another HPGS. This paper introduces a new configuration of these distributed generation units, where WT, PV, SB, and GT are combined to form a new power generation system, known as hybrid power generation system (HPGS). This configuration is classified as a stand-alone HPGS. On the other hand, if this configuration is connected to the utility, it is called as a utility connected HPGS. In this paper, for the first time, the natural gas distribution network is used to deliver the required fuel for the GT of the HPGS, where all operational conditions of this network are considered. New meta-heuristic optimization techniques are also presented for the first time for the HPGS designing. The applied techniques are; the grey wolf optimizer (GWO) and the dragonfly optimizer (DO).

Keywords: Distributed generation, dragonfly optimizer, grey wolf optimizer, hybrid generation system, and renewable energy sources.

I. Introduction

A lot of effort has been done by researchers to solve the power system problems, where they try to satisfy customer requirement by define the propel solutions for the power system problems. The most common problem is the continuous increasing of the power demand, which facing all government and electric companies responsible. Using the multi configurations of the distributed generation units to form the HPGS is considered the most suitable solution for overcoming this challenge. The proposed HPGS consists of WT, PV, SB, GT, and the utility grid, where the GT is fueled from the natural gas distribution network. This network is used for the first time to deliver the fuel (natural gas), and all operational conditions of this network are considered in this paper.

Y. Luo, L. Shi, and G. Tu, reference [1], study the isolated grids, which contain renewable energy sources and energy storage systems. The authors try to determine the size of the hybrid system elements taking into account the reliability requirement and a bi-level control strategy of the isolated grids. The sodium–sulfur battery type is recommended by the authors for the power balance control in the isolated grids based on comparative analysis of current energy storage characteristics and practicability. Finally, both of genetic algorithm and sequential simulation have been applied in order to determine the size of the energy storage system.

L. Liqun and L. Chunxia, reference [2], discuss the feasibility of a standalone hybrid power system, which consists of WT, PV, and SB for a remote village. The simulation model for the proposed hybrid power system is built to obtain its components sizing. Moreover, the authors discuss the greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions, the project costs, savings summary, financial viability, and risk analysis.

In reference [3], Q. A. J. Jawad¹, K. K. Gasem, and M. R. Jawad design and simulate the hybrid system, which consists of WT, PV, and diesel generator. This system has been built to feed the power to an urban area. The authors execute a detailed comparison between different configurations of distributed generation units to decide which one meets the predefined constraints such as; system cost, reliability, and system efficiency. Finally, it is shown that, if the mixed-coupled of DG units has been occurred, the high system efficiency is achieved.

T. Jima, reference [4], presents a design of a hybrid power generation system, where both of wind and solar systems are utilized for supplying the power for wood and metal products factories at the Welenchity site. The author studies the wind and the solar conditions of the mentioned area, where the data of wind speed and solar irradiation are collected. The HOMER software has been applied to design the standalone PV-WT-SB-diesel generator hybrid system.

In reference [5], A. Bhowmik, applies the Microsoft Excel software-programming package to analyze the

collected data of the wind speed and solar irradiance. The author aims to build a hybrid power system consisting of WT, PV, SB, and diesel generator. Moreover, the author applies MATLAB software to develop the simulation model to optimize the objective function of the proposed system. All objective function constraints and parameters boundaries are defined. Finally, the author carried out a comparison between the results obtained from applying Excel and MATLAB software.

H. M. Farghally, F. H. Fahmy, and M. A. H. EL-Sayed, reference [6], study the behavior of some emergency loads such as; hospitals and schools. The energy requirements are defined and studied using the HOMER software. Hybrid power system based on the combination of WT and PV has been planned, and its objective function is defined. The authors apply the above mentioned software to solve the hybrid system objective function. Moreover, a neural network controller is developed to achieve the coordination between system components as well as control the energy flows.

In reference [7], P. Gajbhiye, and P. Suhane study the performance of some critical loads at different weather conditions, where the authors collect the ambient temperature, the solar irradiance, and the wind speed for an urban area. The authors represent a combination from some renewable energy sources to meet the power demand of some loads. As defined, the hybrid system is combined from WT and PV, diesel generator, and SB. However, the diesel generator and the SB have been used to cover the emergency loads under varying weather conditions. The objective function of the WT-PV-SB-diesel generator is defined. And it is claimed that, this study leads to feasible solution for distributed generation of electric power for stand-alone applications for remote locations.

H. Belmili, M. Haddadi, S. Bacha, and M. F. Almi, reference [8], analyze the techno-economic considerations of the WT-PV-SB hybrid system. The objective function of this system is defined considering the loss of power supply probability. Both of genetic algorithm and particle swarm have been used to solve the objective function. Finally, a detailed comparison between the GA and PSO results to show that, the particle swarm gives results more effective than the genetic algorithm.

In reference [9], L. J. Hu, D. M. Xi, S.S. Guo, and Y.J. Fu discuss as claimed a new methodology to determine the hybrid power system capacity. The proposed system consists of WT, PV, and SB, where the system objective function has been designed considering all expected conditions of the hybrid power system. Two different definitions are shown according to the system connection to the utility grid, where if the system is connected to the utility it is termed as the utility connected hybrid power system. While, if it individually supplies the loads, it is termed as a standalone hybrid power system. A computational comparison between the two concepts is executed.

In reference [10], A.M. Eltamaly and M. A. Mohamed introduce a design and simulation program for autonomous hybrid PV-WT-SB hybrid power system. The authors try to determine the size of each component of the hybrid system considering the economic issue and the best loss of load probability at highest reliability. The HOMER software is applied to study the changing of the penetration ratio of WT-PV with certain increments. They calculate the size of all components to get the acceptable probability.

In reference [11], A. Maleki and A. Askarzadeh design the PV-WT-FC hybrid power system. A combination from the meta-heuristic techniques is applied to obtain the hybrid system components size, where it consists of chaotic search (CS), harmony search (HS) and simulated annealing (SA). Finally, a comparison between the CS, HS, and SA obtained results has been carried out to decide which optimization technique gives the most efficient results. It is found as claimed, the combined optimization algorithms give results are better than applying each algorithm individually.

B. Tudu, K. K. Mandal, and N. Chakraborty, in reference [12], present a hybrid power system, which consists of micro-hydro turbine, PV, WT and FC to meet a specific load. The object is to find the components sizing of the proposed hybrid power system. Both of the BCA and PSO are applied to obtain the sizing of hybrid power system components, and the authors compare the results of BCA and PSO. It is claimed that, both of algorithms are capable of giving global solution, but PSO is fast in reaching it.

This paper introduces the optimal design of a new HPGS, which consists of WT, PV, SB, GT, and connected to the utility grid. The natural gas distribution network is included for the first time to fuel the GT with the required natural gas, and all operational conditions are considered in this paper to avoid the increasing of the investment cost, where the design of this system including the natural gas network is the first contribution. This system is classified as a utility connected mode, this mode is studied at two different conditions; winter and summer conditions. In this paper, the winter condition is known as *scenario I*, while the summer condition is defined as *scenario II*. The second contribution in this paper, is the applying the new meta-heuristic optimization techniques such as; GWO and DO for the first time to find the optimal design of the proposed HPGS.

Nomenclature

symbol	Meaning
U	Average velocity
P_b	Absolute pressure at datum conditions (<i>bar</i>).
d	Internal diameter of the pipe (<i>mm</i>)
f	Friction factor
P_1	Absolute input pressure (<i>bar</i>)
P_2	Absolute downstream (outlet) pressure (<i>bar</i>)
L	Length of the pipe (m).
T_s	Standard temperature (288 K)
S	Specific gravity of natural gas

Z	Average compressibility factor
T	Average temperature of the flowing gas
Q_r	Output flow rate from the pressure regulator
K_r	Flow coefficient.
$P_{r,out}$	Output pressure of the pressure regulator in bar
$P_{r,in}$	Input pressure of the pressure regulator
I_i	Initial cost of each power source (WT, PV, SB, and GT).
OM_{P_i}	Operation and maintenance cost for each power source (WT, PV, SB, and GT).
S_{P_i}	Salvage value of each power source (WT, PV, and GT).
N_p	project lifetime
AFC_N	Annual fuel (natural gas) cost.
APC_U	Cost of the annual purchasing electricity.
α_w	Initial cost of wind turbine ($\$/m^2$)
A_w	Swept area (m^2)
α_{OM_w}	Operation and maintenance cost of wind turbine system ($\$/m^2$)
s_w	Salvage value of wind turbine ($\$/m^2$)
β	Inflation rate
γ	Interest rate
α_p	Initial cost of PV system ($\$/m^2$)
A_p	Swept area (m^2)
α_B	Initial cost of storage battery system ($\$/kW$)
P_B	Storage battery capacity (kW)
N_B	Storage battery lifetime
X_B	Number of times to purchase the SB during
α_{OM_B}	Operation and maintenance cost of storage battery system ($\$/kW$).
α_G	Initial cost of gas turbine ($\$/kW$)
P_{cap_G}	Gas turbine capacity (kW)
α_{OM_G}	Operation and maintenance cost of gas turbine system ($\$/kW$)
$P_{U,t}$	Contributed power from the utility grid at hour t in kW
ϕ_P	Electricity price of the utility $\$/kW$

II. Motivation of using the Natural Gas

After many natural gas discoveries at the end of last century, the Egyptian government had decided to replace the applications of the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) by the natural gas to save the rate exchange and to improve the fuel reliability for all customers' categories. Natural gas transmission and distribution networks had been constructed, which are essential to supply the natural gas to the people. Electric power and natural gas load profiles for an urban area have been studied, where the electric power and natural gas loads have been curved in Millions of British Thermal Unit (MBTU). The following points are noted according to the Fig 1, where, the black line refers to the monthly natural gas load profile, the blue line shows the month electric load profile, and the red line describes the average monthly energy consumption in MBTU. This line is created if both of the electricity and natural gas consumptions are converted to MBTU from kW and m^3/h respectively. The following are noted from Fig 1:

- 1- The natural gas (NG) consumption increases during the winter months (01, 02, 03, 04, 11, and 12) and decreases during the summer months (05, 06, 07, 08, 09, and 10).
- 2- The electricity consumption decreases during the winter months and increases during the summer months, which represents exactly the opposite for NG consumption.

Fig 2 describes the daily consumptions of the natural gas and the electricity loads profiles, and the following could be noted from it:

- 1- The off-peak periods of the natural gas loads approximately synchronized with the on-peak periods of the electric power load, and vice versa. This means there is the ability to deliver natural gas to supply the NG to gas turbine without reducing the NG system reliability.

The motivations and the chance of using the natural gas at the distribution level to generate the required electric power for the urban areas are increased according to Fig 1 and Fig 2. Where the abscissa of Fig 1 shows the months and in Fig 2 shows the twenty-four hour of the day. While, the ordinate of the two figures represents the energy loads (electrical and natural gas) in MBTU.

Fig 1 and Fig 2 are obtained from the historical data of the energy (electricity and natural gas) consumptions of the studied area.

III. Problem Formulation

Fig 3 shows a typical hybrid generation system, which consists of different power sources including wind turbine (WT), PV panels (PV), and storage batteries (SB), and the gas turbine (GT). This system also, is connected to the utility grid through the essential power converters. The following sections describe the proposed system.

Fig.1 MBTU consumptions for the studied area

Fig. 2 The daily consumptions of the electric power and natural gas loads

Fig. 3 Configuration of a typical hybrid power generation system

III.1. Description of Natural Gas Distribution Network

Natural gas is transmitted to the domestic areas in medium pressure network (up to 7 bar). This pressure is reduced to 100 mbar through pressure regulator. Fig 4 shows this regulator, which automatically regulates the output pressure through closed loop control system. The red color refers to the medium pressure (input) natural gas and the yellow color shows the low pressure (output) natural gas. According to the manufacture design there is a lower allowable limit for the regulator input pressure. So, the value of the lower allowable limit is considered a system constraint. The pipes flow velocity also is considered another constraint, where if it exceeds a certain limit, the pipe dust will move the natural gas devices and the big deals may be occurred [13][14].

Equation (1) shows the effective factors on the flow velocity (U) such as, the upstream pressure, and the pipe diameter.

$$U = \frac{353Q}{d^2[P_1^2 - \frac{3730fLQ^2}{d^5}]^{0.5}} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4 The 850 VARIFLO natural gas pressure regulator

where,

U is the average velocity of the natural gas flow (m/s)
 Q is the gas flow rate (m^3/h) defined as shown in Equation 2.

$$Q = 7.574 \times T_s \times P_b^{-1} \times f^{-0.5} \{(P_1^2 - P_2^2) \times d^5 (S \times Z \times T \times L)^{-1}\}^{0.5} \times 10^{-4} \quad (2)$$

P_b is the absolute pressure at datum conditions (bar).

d is the internal diameter of the pipe (mm)

f is the friction factor

P_1 is the absolute input pressure (bar)

P_2 is the absolute downstream (outlet) pressure (bar)

L is the length of the pipe (m).

T_s is the standard temperature (288 K)

S is the specific gravity of natural gas

Z is the average compressibility factor

T is the average temperature of the flowing gas

According to Fig 4 the maximum output flow rate from the pressure regulator (Q_r) could be calculated as follows:

$$Q_r = K_r \sqrt{P_{r,out}(P_{r,in} - P_{r,out})} \quad (3)$$

where,

K_r is the flow coefficient.

$P_{r,out}$ is the output pressure of the pressure regulator in bar

$P_{r,in}$ is the input pressure of the pressure regulator. It equals P_2 .

The cubic meters of the natural gas delivered from the main pipeline (Equation 2) are maximized considering the flow velocity and the inlet pressure for the pressure regulators as follows:

$$\text{maximize } Q \quad (4)$$

Subjected to:

$$U \leq 20$$

$$P_{min} \leq P_2 \leq P_1$$

If Equation 1 is solved at P_b equals to 1.01325 bar, P_1 equals to 5.01325 bar, and ≤ 20 m/sec. It is found that, the maximum allowable capacity per hour (m_{max}) from the pipeline is $\leq 4793.48 m^3/hr$. When using all these values at Equation 2, the minimum value of P_2 is 1.47125 bar. Therefore, the maximum allowable limit of the natural gas flow is $4793.48 m^3/hr$ without exceeding the maximum allowable limit of the flow velocity and or exceeding the minimum allowable limit of the input pressure

III.2 Design Objective Functions

Total Annual Cost (TAC)

The first objective function of this system is the total annual cost, where it consists of the initial cost, operations and maintenance cost, salvage value, the annual fuel cost, and the annual purchased electric power from the utility grid. While, the second objective function of this system is the system pollution [15]. All components of the first objective function are represented as the following equations:

$$TAC = \frac{\Sigma(I_i + OM_{P_i} - SP_i)}{NP} + AFC_N + APC_U \quad (5)$$

where,

i indicates the WT, PV, SB, and GT

I_i is the initial cost of each power source (WT, PV, SB, and GT).

OM_{P_i} is the operation and maintenance cost for each power source (WT, PV, SB, and GT).

S_{P_i} is the salvage value of each power source (WT, PV, and GT).

N_P is the project lifetime.

AFC_N is the annual fuel (natural gas) cost.

APC_U is the cost of the annual purchasing electricity.

For the wind turbine (WT); Equation 6 shows the initial cost, Equation 7 shows the operation and maintenance cost, and Equation 8 shows the salvage value of the wind turbine.

$$I_w = \alpha_w \cdot A_w \quad (6)$$

where,

α_w is the initial cost of wind turbine (\$/m²)

A_w is the swept area (m²)

$$OM_w = \alpha_{OM_w} \cdot A_w \sum_{i=1}^{N_P} \left(\frac{1+v}{1+\gamma}\right)^i \quad (7)$$

where,

α_{OM_w} is the operation and maintenance cost of wind turbine system (\$/m²)

v is the escalation factor

$$S_w = s_w \cdot A_w \left(\frac{1+\beta}{1+\gamma}\right)^{N_P} \quad (8)$$

where,

s_w is the salvage value of wind turbine (\$/m²)

β is the inflation rate

γ is the interest rate

For the photovoltaic (PV) system; the total annual cost of the PV system likes the total annual cost of the wind turbine, where Equations 9, 10, and 11 show the initial cost, the operation and maintenance cost, the salvage cost respectively.

$$I_P = \alpha_P \cdot A_P \quad (9)$$

where,

α_P is the initial cost of PV system (\$/m²)

A_P is the swept area (m²)

$$OM_P = \alpha_{OM_P} \cdot A_P \sum_{i=1}^{N_P} \left(\frac{1+v}{1+\gamma}\right)^i \quad (10)$$

$\alpha_{OM_{PV}}$ is the operation and maintenance cost of PV system (\$/m²)

$$S_P = s_P \cdot A_P \left(\frac{1+\beta}{1+\gamma}\right)^{N_P} \quad (11)$$

where,

s_P is the salvage value of PV system (\$/m²)

For the storage battery (SB) system; it has only the initial cost and the operation and maintenance cost, and there is no salvage value because the aged batteries should be disposed according to the international environmental regulations. Equation 12 shows the initial cost of the SB, and its lifetime is lower than the project lifetime, and Equation 13 shows the operation and maintenance cost.

$$I_B = \alpha_B \cdot P_{Bcap} \sum_{i=1}^{X_B} \left(\frac{1+v}{1+\beta}\right)^{(i-1)N_B} \quad (12)$$

where,

α_B is the initial cost of storage battery system (\$/kW)

P_B is the storage battery capacity (kW)

N_B is the storage battery lifetime

X_B is the number of times to purchase the SB during the project lifespan N_P .

$$OM_B = \alpha_{OM_B} \cdot P_{Bcap} \sum_{i=1}^{N_P} \left(\frac{1+v}{1+\gamma}\right)^i \quad (13)$$

α_{OM_B} is the operation and maintenance cost of storage battery system (\$/kW).

For the gas turbine (GT); it has annual initial cost, annual operation and maintenance cost, annual salvage cost, and annual fuel cost as shown in Equations 14, 15, 16, and 17 respectively.

$$I_G = \alpha_G \cdot P_{cap_G} \quad (14)$$

where,

α_G is the initial cost of gas turbine (\$/kW)

P_{cap_G} is the gas turbine capacity (kW)

$$OM_G = \alpha_{OM_G} \cdot P_{cap_G} \sum_{i=1}^{N_P} \left(\frac{1+v}{1+\gamma}\right)^i \quad (15)$$

where,

α_{OM_G} is the operation and maintenance cost of gas turbine system (\$/kW)

$$S_G = s_G \cdot P_{cap_G} \left(\frac{1+\beta}{1+\gamma}\right)^{N_P} \quad (16)$$

where, s_G is the salvage value of gas turbine (\$/kW)

$$APC_N = \sum_{t=1}^{8760} m \cdot \varphi_N \quad (17)$$

m is the consumed m³/h by the GT. φ_N is the cost of the cubic meter of the natural gas (\$/m³/h).

Equation 18 describes the total annual cost of the purchased electricity from the utility grid per year.

$$APC_U = \sum_{t=1}^{8760} P_{U,t} \times \varphi_P \quad (18)$$

where, $P_{U,t}$ is the contributed power from the utility grid at hour t in kW. φ_P is the electricity price of the utility \$/kW

Pollutant Emissions

There are a lot of emissions have been result due to the using fossil fuels at the power plants, which have the bad impact on the health and the environment such as; sulfur dioxide (SO₄) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) [1].

These emissions could be measured as follows:

$$PE = k_1 + k_2 \times \sum_{t=1}^T (P_{U,t} + P_{G,t}) + k_3 \times \left(\sum_{t=1}^T (P_{U,t} + P_{G,t})\right)^2 \quad (19)$$

where,

$P_{G,t}$ is the generated power from the gas turbine at hour t in KW and it is described as shown in Equation 20 [16].

$$P_G = \eta_G \times m \times HHV_G \quad (20)$$

where, η_G is the gas turbine and the alternator overall efficiency. HHV_G is the high heat value in mega-joule per cubic meter MJ/m³. k_1, k_2 and k_3 are

the coefficients approximating the generation power emission characteristics.

Design Constraints

There are some constraints should be satisfied throughout the optimization of the HPGS objective functions [15]. At any hour t , the total power supply from the hybrid generation system must meet the total demand $P_d(t)$ including the system loss as shown in Equation 21.

$$P_w(t) + P_p(t) + P_B(t) + P_U(t) + P_G(t) = P_d(t) \quad (21)$$

Assuming that, the system loss is included into the $P_d(t)$. where, If the wind speed is less than the cut-in speed (V_{ci}) of the wind turbine the delivered power from the wind turbine is zero. Equation 22 shows the output power of the wind turbine in case of wind speed is between the cut-in speed (V_{ci}) and the rated speed (V_r) of the wind turbine.

$$P_w(t) = \frac{1}{2} \rho \times A_w \times V_t^3 \times C_p \times \eta_w \quad (22)$$

The rated power of the wind turbine is delivered when the wind speed is between the rated speed (V_r) and the cut-off speed (V_{co}). At the last, the wind turbine comes off when the wind speed exceeds the cut-off speed. Equation 23 shows the output power of the PV system.

$$P_p(t) = H_p \times A_p \times \eta_p \quad (23)$$

H is the solar irradiance in KW/m^2 . η_p is the efficiency of the PV system.

A. Bounds of Design Variables

Both of Equation 24 and 25 show the upper and the lower limits of the swept area of the wind turbine and PV system respectively.

$$A_{wmin} \leq A_w \leq A_{wmax} \quad (24)$$

$$A_{pmin} \leq A_p \leq A_{pmax} \quad (25)$$

There are some operational conditions should be considered during the design of the storage battery system. Basically, the state of charge (SOC) of the batteries system P_{Bsoc} should not exceed the capacity of storage batteries P_{SBcap} . Also, it should be higher than the minimum permissible storage level P_{Bmin} , as shown in Equation (26).

$$P_{Bmin} \leq P_{Bsoc} \leq P_{Bcap} \quad (26)$$

Equation (27) shows the total SB capacity should not exceed the allowed storage capacity $P_{Bcapmax}$.

$$0 \leq P_{Bcap} \leq P_{Bcapmax} \quad (27)$$

Finally, the hourly charge or discharge power P_B should not exceed the hourly inverter capacity P_{Bmax} as described in Equation (28).

$$P_B \leq P_{Bmax} \quad (28)$$

Equation 29 illustrates that the flow rate (natural gas consumption) of the gas turbine fuel should not exceed

the maximum allowable limit which is shown in section 2.

$$m_{min} < m < m_{max} \quad (29)$$

The delivered power per hour from the utility should not exceed the maximum permitted limit as contracted with the electricity company.

$$P_{Umin} < P_U < P_{Umax} \quad (30)$$

IV. Applied Meta-Heuristic Techniques

The following section introduces the applied meta-heuristic optimization techniques, where in this paper, both of GWO and DO have been applied using MATLAB software to find the optimal HPGS system components size for the utility connected mode.

IV.1. Grey Wolf Optimizer

This technique simulates the hunting behavior of the grey wolf. The authors divide the wolves according to their role during the hunting process. The main categories of the wolf are alpha, beta, delta, and omega as shown in Fig 5 [17].

Fig 5 The main types of grey wolves

The first type, Alpha takes the hunting decision, then the second one, beta type tips the alpha type. Third type is delta, which helps the alpha and beta types during the prey hunting, moreover it provides food for the other wolves. The last one is termed as omega, where this type provides the support for the weak, and ill ones. Equation 31 shows how the wolf position is changed and how it is updated according to the prey hunting process.

$$\vec{X}_w(t+1) = \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{A}_w \cdot \vec{D}_w \quad (31)$$

where, \vec{X}_p is the position vector of the prey. \vec{A}_w is the coefficient vector, and it is represented as in Equation 32.

$$\vec{A}_w = 2 \cdot \vec{a} \cdot \vec{r}_1 - \vec{a} \quad (32)$$

\vec{D}_w is the position of each wolf from any type, and it is represented as in Equation (33).

$$\vec{D}_w = |\vec{C}_w \cdot \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{X}_w(t)| \quad (33)$$

\vec{C}_w is the coefficient vector. It is represented as in (34).

$$\vec{C}_w = 2 \cdot \vec{r}_2 \quad (34)$$

\vec{a} is linearly reduced from 2 to 0 during the iterations.

\vec{r}_1 and \vec{r}_2 are arbitrary vectors $\in [0, 1]$.

GWO pseudo code

Initialize the Grey Wolf population $X_i = (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$

Initialize a, A, C

Calculate the fitness of each search agent

X_α = the best search agent

X_β = the second best search agent

X_δ = the third best search agent

While ($t < \text{Max Number of Iteration}$)

 for every search agent

 Update the position the current search agent

 end for

Update a, A, C

Calculate the fitness of all agents

Update $X_\alpha, X_\beta, X_\delta$

$t = t + 1$

end while

Return X_α

IV.2. Dragonfly Optimizer

This algorithm simulates the life style of the dragonfly, where all common action of it are simulated such as; travelling, searching for food, and fighting for survival. Equation 35 models the behavior of searching for food of the dragonfly, while Equation 36 represents the dragonfly scape from any galloper [18].

$$F_i = X^+ - X \quad (35)$$

where, X^+ is the position of the food source. X is the position of the current individual.

$$E_i = X^- - X \quad (36)$$

where,

X^- shows the position of the galloper.

The updated position vectors of the dragonfly are represented as follows:

$$X_{t+1} = X_t + \Delta X_{t+1} \quad (37)$$

where,

X_t is position vectors at iteration t . ΔX_{t+1} is the step from X_t to X_{t+1} .

The above equation did not consider the random walk of the dragonfly. So, it is replaced by Equation 38.

$$X_{t+1} = X_t + \text{Lévy}(d) \times X_t \quad (38)$$

Where,

d is the dimension of the position vectors.

The following shows the DO pseudo code:

DO pseudo code

Initialize the dragonflies' population X_i ($i = 1, 2,$

\dots, n) Initialize step vectors ΔX_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots,$

n) while the end condition is not satisfied

 Calculate the objective values of all dragonflies

 Update the food source

 Calculate F and E using Equations 36 and 37

 Update neighboring radius

 if a dragonfly has at least one neighboring

 dragonfly Update velocity vector

 Update position vector using

Equation 38

 else

 Update position vector using

Equation 39

 end if

 Check and correct the new positions based on the boundaries of variables

end while

V. Application to Case Study

This paper introduces the design of the hybrid power system, which consists of WT, PV, SB, and GT, and it is connected to the utility grid. Two modern meta-heuristic techniques; GWO and DO have been applied to find the optimal design of the proposed hybrid power system. This system is designed at two different scenarios; summer and winter to consider all weather conditions. Table 1 shows the data of the overall system required

parameters. Table 2 gives the data of the average power demand, the average wind speed, the average solar irradiance, and the average natural gas demand at the different weather conditions [15].

TABLE I
THE DATA OF THE USED SYSTEM PARAMETERS

System parameters	Values	Unit
the abs. pressure P_b	1.013	bar
the internal dia. of the pipe d	173	mm
the friction factor f	0.135	
the abs. upstream pressure P_1	5.013	bar
the length of the pipe L	1000	m
the standard temperature T_s	288	K
the spec. gravity of natural gas S	0.6	Kg/m ³
the ave. compressibility factor Z	0.99	
the ave. temp. of the gas T	278	K
regulator P_{out}	1.1013	bar
the flow coefficient K_r	2000	
Wind turbine efficiency η_w	50 %	
PV efficiency η_p	16 %	
Storage battery efficiency η_B	82 %	
Inflation rate β	9 %	
Interest rate γ	12 %	
Escalation rate v	12 %	
Lifespan of the project N_p	20	year
Lifespan of the wind turbine	20	year
Lifespan of the PV	20	year
Lifespan of the Storage battery	10	year
Wind turbine initial cost α_w	100	\$/m ²
PV initial cost α_v	450	\$/m ²
Storage Battery initial cost α_B	100	\$/kW
Wind turbine salvage value S_w	10	\$/m ²
PV salvage value S_p	45	\$/m ²
Op. & Main. cost of WT α_{OM_w}	2.5	\$/m ²
Op. & Main. cost of PV α_{OM_v}	4.3	\$/m ²
Op. & Main. cost of SB α_{OM_B}	10.0	\$/kW
Wind turbine rated power P_{WT_r}	4.0	kw
Max. swept area of WT A_w	10000	m ²
Min. swept area of WT $A_{w_{min}}$	400	m ²
Max. swept area of PV A_{PV}	8000	m ²
Min. swept area of WT A_{PV}	200	m ²
Minimum storage level $P_{b_{min}}$	150	kW
Rated battery capacity P_{b_r}	250	kW
Max. SB capacity $P_{b_{cap_{max}}}$	500	kW
Price of utility grid power ϕ	0.092	\$/kW
k_1	4.09	
k_2	-5.5	
k_3	6.5	

TABLE II
INPUT DATA AT THE DIFFERENT WEATHER CONDITIONS

System parameters	Scenario I	Scenario II
Ave. power load (kW)	1500	2700
Ave. wind speed (m/s)	5.3	4.87
Ave. solar irradiance (w/m ²)	100.5	172.8
Ave. natural gas load (m ³ /hr)	850	645

VI. Results

Both of GWO and DO have been applied to find the optimal design of hybrid power generation

system. Table III shows a comparison between the results of applying the GWO and DO for designing the hybrid system at winter conditions (scenario I). The resulted annual cost of this system in this case is \$550,013 and \$545,786 by applying GWO and DO respectively. The required natural gas is less than 100m³/hr for using GWO, while it is 112 m³/hr using DO. Therefore, the total required amount of it for the first scenario is 932.24m³/hr and 962 m³/hr by applying GWO and DO respectively. The main constraints of using the natural gas distribution network might be checked using *synerGEE* software. And it is found according to the total required amount of the natural gas that, the flow velocity (U) is less than the maximum allowable limit 20m/sec. Moreover, the input pressure of the regulator is more than the minimum allowable limit. The total system emission (in ton of CO₂/ year) is 1.62 × 10¹⁰ and it is 1.63 × 10¹⁰ using GWO and DO respectively. This table could be represented on another form, where Fig 6 shows a bar chart of the total annual cost, and Fig 7 shows the total system emission.

TABLE III
DESIGN OF THE WT-PV-SB-GT-UTILITY GRID HPGS AT SCENARIO I USING GWO AND DA

Parameters	GWO	DO
A_{WT} (m ²)	10000	10000
A_{PV} (m ²)	569	534
$P_{SB_{cap}}$ (kW)	500	500
P_{UT} (kW)	190	210
P_{GT} (kW)	343	365
NG (m ³ /hr)	96.62	112
Cost (\$/year)	550,013	545,786
Emission (ton/year)	1.62 × 10 ¹⁰	1.63 × 10 ¹⁰

Fig. 6 TAC of WT-PV-SB-GT-utility grid HPGS at scenario I using GWO and DO

Table IV shows the comparison of the hybrid power system designing result at summer conditions (scenario II). The high temperature of the summer season has the impacts on some important factors, whereas the ambient temperature increases the natural gas consumption decreased as shown in Table II. Also, the consumption of

the electricity increased as the temperature increased due to the increasing of using the electrical cooling devices. In this case, the electrical demand is $2700kW/hr$, and the meta-heuristic optimization techniques have been used to optimize the system cost function, which is constrained by the power demand function as shown in Equation 5. Both of GWO and DO are applied to minimize the total annual cost and the total system emission functions. The total annual cost obtained of this system is $\$1,550,814/year$ and $\$1,542,875/year$ using GWO and DO respectively. The total required amount from the natural gas for the heating loads and the electricity generation is $997.68 m^3/hr$ and $1032.03 m^3/hr$ using GWO and DO respectively. These values approximately equal the value of the total natural gas consumptions of scenario I, where all value around the value of $1000m^3/hr$ at the different weather conditions. Also, these values did not exceed the maximum allowable limit of the pipes capacity. Therefore, the flow velocity is lower than the maximum allowable limit and the input pressure of the gas regulator does not be lower than the minimum allowable limit. Also, this table may be represented on another form, where Fig 8 shows a bar chart of the total annual cost, and Fig 9 shows the total system annual pollution.

Fig. 7 SP of WT-PV-SB-GT- utility grid HPGS at scenario I using GWO and DO

TABLE IV
DESIGN OF THE WT-PV-SB-GT-UTILITY GRID HPGS AT SCENARIO II USING GWO AND DA

Parameters	GWO	DA
$A_{WT} (m^2)$	9871	10000
$A_{PV} (m^2)$	6824	5281
$P_{SBcap} (kW)$	500	500
$P_{WT} (kW)$	409	521
$P_{GT} (kW)$	1252	1305
NG (m^3/hr)	352.68	387.03
Cost ($\$/year$)	1,550,814	1,542,875
Emission (ton/year)	1.57×10^{11}	1.58×10^{11}

Fig. 8 TAC of WT-PV-SB-GT-utility grid HPGS at scenario II using GWO and DA

Fig. 9 SP of WT-PV-SB-GT-utility grid HPGS at scenario II using GWO and DO

VII. Conclusion

This paper discusses a new configuration of different distributed generation units to form a new HPGS, where it consists of WT, PV, SB, and GT. In this case it is called as a standalone hybrid power system, while if this combination is connected to the utility grid, it is called to utility grid mode. This paper discusses only the utility grid mode at two different weather conditions; winter (scenario I) and summer (scenario II). The natural gas distribution network is included in the HPGS for the first time to fuel the GT with the natural gas. Therefore, the using of the natural gas distribution network is considered the first contribution in this paper, where all operational conditions of this network are considered such as; the network pressure drop, and the flow velocity. This paper describes in details the objective functions of this system, where there are two objective functions; the total annual cost (TAC) and the system pollution (SP). The first function consists of the initial cost, operations and maintenance cost, salvage value, and the annual cost of the purchased electricity and natural gas, considering the interest rate, escalation factor, and depreciation rate. New meta-heuristic optimization techniques are applied to solve the objective functions of this system. The applied techniques are GWO and DO, which are used for the first time in this kind of applications, which considered the second contribution in this paper. It is found that, DO gives results with respect to the TAC are more effective than the GWO, while the later technique gives results with respect to the SP are more effective than the first one.

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